

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furocoumarins

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7-Hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin has been condensed with malic acid to yield 3,4-dimethylcoumarino-7,8- α -pyrone, also obtained by the Perkin acetylation of 7-hydroxy-8-formyl-3,4-dimethylcoumarin. The structure of the formyl derivative has been proved by the Dakin oxidation to the known 7,8-dihydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin. The latter and 5-hydroxy-3,4,7-trimethylcoumarin on a similar condensation with malic acid provide 3,4-dimethyl-8-hydroxycoumarino-7,8- α -pyrone and 3,4,7-trimethylcoumarino-5,6- α -pyrone respectively.

7-Hydroxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin has been condensed with malic acid to afford 3-bromo-4-methylcoumarino-7,8- α -pyrone which has also been obtained on bromination of 4-methylcoumarino-7,8- α -pyrone. It has been degraded to furo-3'-methyl-4',5'-5,6-coumarin. This is a new approach to the synthesis of furocoumarins.

Hantzsch and Zurcher condensed resorcinol and phloroglucinol with 2 and 3 moles of ethyl acetoacetate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid and obtained coumarino- α -pyrone derivatives. Sen and Chakravarti² on a similar condensation of umbelliferone, 4-methylumbelliferone, daphnetin, 4-methyl-daphnetin, 5,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, and homoumbelliferone with malic acid obtained the corresponding coumarino- α -pyrones in good yields. Rangaswami and Seshadri³ have shown that when umbelliferone is condensed with malic acid, both the linear and the angular coumarino- α -pyrones are obtained, the former in poor yield. The present work deals with the synthesis of some substituted coumarino- α -pyrones and a study of their conversion to furocoumarins.

7-Hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin was condensed with malic acid. The product obtained was found to be 3,4-dimethylcoumarino-7,8- α -pyrone, identical with the product obtained on the Perkin acetylation of 7-hydroxy-8-formyl-3,4-dimethylcoumarin. The formyl derivative, prepared by the action of hexamine on 7-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin, on the Dakin oxidation afforded the known 7,8-dihydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin⁴.

7,8-Dihydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin and 5-hydroxy-3,4,7-trimethylcoumarin on a similar condensation with malic acid furnished 3,4-dimethyl-8-hydroxycoumarino-7,8- α -pyrone and 3,4,7-trimethylcoumarino-5,6- α -pyrone. Attempts to condense 7-hydroxy-4,8-dimethyl- and 7-hydroxy-4,6-dimethyl-coumarin with malic acid did not succeed.

7-Hydroxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin on condensation with malic acid afforded 3-bromo-4-methylcoumarino-7,8- α -pyrone (I) which was also obtained by brominating

1 Ber, 1887, 20, 1328.

2. This *Journal*, 1929, 6, 793.

3 *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 6A, 112.

4. Canter et al., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1877.

4-methylcoumarino-7,8- α -pyrone. The bromo derivative was converted into furo-3'-methyl-4',5'-5,6-coumarin-2'-carboxylic acid (II) on hydrolysis with ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution. On decarboxylation it furnished furo-3'-methyl-4',5'-5,6-coumarin (III), obtained previously by Shah and Shah⁵ by a different route. This is a new approach to the synthesis of furocoumarins.

On a similar condensation, 7,8-dihydroxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin yielded 3-bromo-4-methyl-8-hydroxycoumarino-7,6- α -pyrone. Attempts to methylate this compound with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate, either in benzene or acetone, by refluxing the reaction mixture for 48 hours did not succeed. Its hydrolysis with ethanolic KOH or sodium carbonate solution with a view to synthesising 3-methylxanthotoxol resulted in an unworkable mass.

Attempts to condense 7-hydroxy-3,8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-3,6-dibromocoumarin with malic acid did not succeed.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Procedure for Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones.—A mixture of the coumarin derivative (5 g.), malic acid (5 g.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 5 ml) was heated on a water bath till effervescence of carbon monoxide had ceased (about 3 to 4 hrs.). The product separating on adding the reaction mixture to crushed ice was treated with ammonia and filtered. It was crystallised from acetic acid. In the case of 3,4-dimethyl-8-hydroxycoumarino-7,6- α -pyrone and 3-bromo-4-methyl-8-hydroxycoumarino-7,6- α -pyrone, the separated product was refluxed with large quantities of absolute ethanol instead of ammonia to remove the original coumarin and the residue was crystallised from pyridine (Table I).

7-Hydroxy-8-formyl-3,4-dimethylcoumarin.—A mixture of 7-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (10 g.), hexamine (10 g.), and glacial acetic acid (100 ml) was gently refluxed on a sand bath for 10 hours. HCl (100 ml, 1:1) was then added and the mixture heated for 5 hours on a steam bath. The product obtained on extraction with ether was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 185-87°. It developed a deep red colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 65.76; H, 4.38. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.08; H, 4.62%).

⁵ Shah and Shah, *this Journal*, 1940, 17, 41.

*All m. p.s. are uncorrected.

The 2,4-*DNP*, prepared as usual, melted at 290° (decomp.). (Found, N, 14.48. $C_{18}H_{14}O_7N_4$ requires N, 14.06%).

7,8-Dihydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin.—The above formylcoumarin (0.5 g.) in 20% NaOH solution (10 ml) at 0° was treated with 6% H_2O_2 (3 ml) dropwise at 0°; the reaction mixture was stirred for an hour and then acidified. The separated product was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles (0.1 g.), m.p. 272°. Mixed m.p. with 7,8-dihydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin, prepared according to Cantor *et al.*⁴, was not depressed. (Found: C, 64.12; H, 4.65. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$: C, 64.07; H, 4.8%).

TABLE I

Coumarino- α -pyrone	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
3,4-Dimethyl-C-7,8- α -P	285-87°	1.5 g.	$C_{14}H_{10}O_4$	C : 69.58% H : 2.95	69.42% 4.16
3,4,7-Trimethyl-C-5,6- α -P	262°	1.0	$C_{15}H_{12}O_4$	C : 69.93 H : 4.55	70.30 4.72
3-Bromo-4-methyl-C-7,8- α -P	335°	0.5	$C_{13}H_7O_4Br$	C : 50.65 H : 2.64 Br : 26.44	50.18 2.28 26.07
3,4-Dimethyl-8-hydroxy-C-7,6- α -P	> 400°	0.7	$C_{14}H_{10}O_5$	C : 65.26 H : 4.28	65.12 3.90
3-Bromo-4-methyl-8-hydroxy-C-7,6- α -P	> 400°	0.5	$C_{13}H_7O_5Br$	C : 48.60 H : 3.53 Br : 24.31	48.30 2.16 24.70
C denotes coumarino.					
P ,, pyrone.					

Perkin Acetylation.—The formyl derivative (0.82 g., 0.04M) on Perkin acetylation with sodium acetate (0.66 g., 0.008 M) and acetic anhydride (2 ml) by heating for 8 hours at 180° afforded 3,4-dimethylcoumarino-7,8- α -pyrone, described above.

Furo-3'-methyl-4',5',5,6-coumarin-2'-carboxylic Acid.—3-Bromo-4-methylcoumarino-7,8- α -pyrone (0.5 g.) was dissolved in hot EtOH-KOH solution (10 ml, 10%) and gently refluxed for 4 hours. The product obtained on acidification was dried and extracted with benzene. The product from benzene extract was recrystallised from benzene (charcoal) in white needles (0.1 g.), m.p. 294°. (Found: C, 63.87; H, 3.69. $C_{13}H_9O_5$ requires C, 63.94; H, 3.30%).

Furo-3'-methyl-4',5',5,6-coumarin.—A mixture of the preceding carboxylic acid (0.5 g.), copper powder (1 g.), and quinoline (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 to 5 hours. The product obtained on working up as usual was crystallised from very dilute ethanol in tiny colorless needles, m.p. 134°. Shah and Shah⁵ reported m.p. 138-40°. (Found: C, 71.98; H, 4.13. Calc. for $C_{11}H_8O_5$: C, 72.0; H, 4.0%).